

D1.4 EOSC Portal SLA, SRM, Privacy Policy

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Abstract:

This document sets out a draft agreement structure for EOSC, focused on the EOSC portal but accommodating the wider EOSC ecosystem. It suggests how agreements relate to one another, their structure, and some initial content. It then touches on the reporting resulting from these agreements, and on existing privacy policies for EOSC portal. These will be consulted on with the EOSC community in 2020 before implementation in 2021.

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Executive Summary

This document proposes an agreement structure for EOSC. This includes two main services to be provided by the EOSC legal entity (EOSC Association AISBL). For researchers and other end users: the provision of EOSC exchange and a catalogue of services and other resources they can access and order. For providers of research services and other resources: the listing and exposure of their services and other resources to a wider pool of potential users and offering other added value features. Other agreements then support these two primary ones, binding in other actors into the EOSC ecosystem.

These agreements should all be assigned to the Exchange User Agreement, made with (largely researcher) users and customers of EOSC, as development and processes should be driven primarily by their needs, and to provide value to them. This will be the 'Portal SLA'.

The contents of the agreements in the structure should all be broadly aligned, similar to one another in form and structure, and based on best practices for service agreements. Given the academic and often non-commercial context of the agreements, they will likely not be accompanied by binding legal contracts and feature penalties. Instead they need to convey to customers what they can expect from EOSC, how services will be delivered, what service levels are targeted, and what will happen when service levels are breached. This will help to create a sense of trust, and a set of good relationships based on open communication and shared ideas of what EOSC can and should provide. This will assist in the development and evolution of EOSC.

Service reporting will be based on the promises and planned reporting in the agreements encompassed in the structure and it will focus on the performance against the targets in those agreements.

Privacy policies for EOSC portal are already in place, and will need to be extended and adapted once the actors and parties to agreements are clear, to ensure that data is adequately protected and all parties can use EOSC with confidence.

The contents of this document will be offered for community review thorough the EOSC interest groups in Q4 2020, to gain feedback from the various actors who will be parties to the agreements. Initial versions of the agreements will then be implemented by EOSC Enhance in 2021 together with the project funded by INFRAEOSC03 and due to start in January 20201, which will also be a major actor in this picture.

Following this, plans will be made for transfer of the agreement structure to the EOSC legal entity, either at the conclusion of Enhance, or at the conclusion of the INFRAEOSC03 project, as appropriate.

1 Introduction

This document sets out an initial structure and suggested contents for the Service Level Management (SLM) and Service Reporting Management (SRM) of the EOSC Portal, as well as suggestions for the Portal Privacy Policy. These are aspects of IT Service Management (ITSM), a well-established professional approach to the management and delivery of IT services across all sectors. This document seeks to advance these topics in light of the work done to date on the portal and also of the evolving situation around EOSC, including the Enhance Project, other projects such as EOSC-hub and OpenAIRE Advance, as well as the newly formed EOSC Association AISBL. Apart from initial steps and suggestions for current agreements or service level specifications, it also makes some suggestions for longer term arrangements in the next project phase and beyond.

2 EOSC Portal: Background and current status

EOSC Portal was launched at the end of 2018 as a collaboration between the EOSC-hub project, and the then-operating eInfraCentral projects, as a ‘frontend’ for the emerging efforts in EOSC and a place to list the (then) two lists of services that were being collated, the catalogue from eInfraCentral and the Marketplace from EOSC-hub. Early versions of the Portal maintained the two separate sources of data in parallel, and they have been progressively merged over the time since, with the final internal integration happening in Q3 2020.

Figure 1: Evolution of EOSC portal and onboarding Evolution of EOSC portal and onboarding.

In December 2019, EOSC Enhance project launched, featuring partners from both EOSC-hub and eInfraCentral as well as from others such as OpenAIRE and the thematic EOSC cluster projects. With it, it

brings a cohesive onboarding process to a single database of services, stored in a Provider Portal and exposed through a shared Marketplace. This can be used to onboard any provider, but the same system will also support transfer of resource metadata (i.e. listings in the provider portal and marketplace) in EOSC portal from other regional or thematic catalogues.

Together this forms a ‘system of systems’ approach, where EOSC portal provides comprehensive access to EOSC resources, but is not a single point of entry forced on the communities that make up EOSC. In this case, by EOSC Resources we mean the full range of entities which might be provided to and accessed through EOSC. EOSC Resources therefore include Services, Data and Data sources, and other Research Products such as publications, software and documents. As this document deals with services and service management, these will be the topic of much of its discussion, but the majority of the content can and will be applied to others EOSC resources as well.

While a ‘System of Systems’ is a powerful approach, this also makes the SLM and SRM inherent in such a system quite complex, as it must accommodate multiple stakeholders and relationship types. This is similar to the SLM and SRM of federated service provisions scenarios, which are already being addressed to some extent through the EOSC Service Management System developed by EOSC-hub.

Figure 2: System of Systems approach to EOSC

The diagram above illustrates this approach. For researchers and other end users, they remain free to use any portal, whether it is a thematic, regional or the central EOSC portal, each bringing different benefits. As metadata on services and other resources can be shared between portals, as long as portals choose to make their metadata shareable and compliant with community standards, they can find the same resources irrespective of where they search. At present this picture is still being created, and as of Summer 2020. EOSC Enhance and the community are still implementing mainly the central integrated EOSC Portal, with plans for the connection between marketplaces planned for later in the year. Nonetheless, in order to make the SLM, SRM and privacy policies work effectively, they must be planned to accommodate the future needs of EOSC as well as the current transitional situation .

3 SLM and SRM in context

This section explains the meaning of SLM and SRM in the broader context of ITSM and a Service Management system. Later sections then apply this more directly to the EOSC case.

Service Level Management and Service reporting management are two typical processes in the context of IT Service Management, a set of approaches and frameworks used to deliver professional and well managed IT services across the commercial public and research sectors. For the purposes of this document, we will use the definitions and approaches from the FitSM standard for IT Service management, which is used in the EOSC Service Management system, and was created via an FP7 project, in part to support the federated scenarios seen in the e-Infrastructure and now EOSC domain. FitSM is also Creative Commons licensed, so parts of it can be reproduced here, however it is compatible with other major ITSM approaches, and the descriptions of SLM and SRM below can be applied to ITSM in general.

Service Level Management (According to FitSM) has the following objective:

*To maintain a service catalogue, and to **define, agree and monitor service levels with customers by establishing meaningful service level agreements (SLAs) and supportive operational level agreements (OLAs) and underpinning agreements (UAs) with suppliers***¹.

In bold, the part which applies to this document is that Service Level Management defines SLAs and other supporting agreements for services. This deliverable is intended to cover a Service Level Agreement (SLA, the most important of these agreements) for the portal, but must also consider supporting agreements such as OLA and UAs which support the SLA. As will be explained later, in reality this will be multiple agreements, aligned to an SLA between the portal operators and end users (largely researchers) for use of the portal.

Figure 3: Agreement types in a Service Management System²

¹ From FitSM 2 Objectives and Activities, edition 2016 v2.2. CC-BY <https://www.fitsm.eu/download/304/>

² From FitSM Foundation Training 2.11 PDF CC-BY <https://www.fitsm.eu/download/360/>

For the purposes of this document, we will use the definition of a service Level Agreement from the FitSM standard:

Service Level Agreement: Documented agreement between a customer and service provider that specifies the service to be provided and the service targets that define how it will be provided.³

More broadly, SLAs represent a shared understanding between a customer and provider as to how a service will be delivered, with what features, under what constraints, and with what service levels or quality of service. It may be linked to or accompanied by a legal contract (often including penalties for SLA violation) but this is not required or always used. In the EOSC domain, SLAs tend to demonstrate an intention or plan for service quality rather than a cast iron guarantee. From an ITSM perspective, this is a valid approach in this situation. Underpinning agreements with providers, or Operational Level Agreements with internal groups of members of the same federation, are supporting agreements which provide components needed to provide services to customers (As covered under SLAs).

In general, in order for SLAs to be meaningful and useful, they must be in place for all services, related to a clear portfolio of services offered, provide clear indication of service levels through Service Level Targets which should be monitored, and should be periodically reviewed with customers. They serve as the input to a vast number of other processes and elements of a service management system, much of which takes input from the promises made in an SLA. For instance promises about the availability of services will drive Service Availability and Continuity management, and performance promises will drive Capacity management.

Service Reporting Management is then driven by SLAs, which typically list the key reports to be made to customers on the services they make use of. SRM then specifies such reports in more detail and ensures they are created and disseminated. The objective of SRM is thus “To specify all service reports and ensure they are produced according to specifications in a timely manner to support decision-making”⁴.

In order to apply these concepts to EOSC we must define who are the customer types, what types of service (or other resources) are to be offered, and how involved each actor will be in EOSC which is a challenging set of questions. In essence it asks us to suggest the main outputs of a Service Portfolio Management process. Once we have a mapping to the EOSC ecosystem, we can suggest specific types of agreement.

4 Planned portal agreement structure

In this section we set out a plan for the agreement structure needed to underlie EOSC and the EOSC portal. Multiple versions are presented to try and accommodate the different evolutions of the EOSC service delivery structures known or predicted over the period 2020-2028.

³ From FitSM 0 Overview and vocabulary, edition 2017 v2.4. CC-BY <https://www.fitsm.eu/download/280/>

⁴ From FitSM 2 Objectives and Activities, edition 2016 v2.2. CC-BY <https://www.fitsm.eu/download/304/>

4.1 Agreement types and roles

Due to the complexity of the imagined EOSC ecosystem, we foresee at least four agreements being required, three SLAs and one OLA. These are summarised in the following diagram. Arrows show service provided, from provider to customer.

Figure 4: Potential agreement structure for future EOSC. Arrows point from provider to customer of services.

The main 'Portal SLA' as imagined in the document title would be the **Exchange User Agreement**. This would cover use of the Marketplace and portal by customers and users wishing to access services and other research related resources. It would describe the conditions under which the Marketplace platform could be used and what guarantees there would be for it. It is in effect an SLA but titled this way to avoid confusion with SLAs for research services and to It would likely include availability of the marketplace, how support would be handled, hours of operation and support and other factors related to the platform. However it would explicitly not cover the actual delivery of research services which may be discovered or ordered via the portal (see section on SLAs for research services below).

The second agreement would be the **Exchange Provider SLA**, to cover the provision of services from the Portal owner to the providers of services and other resources – with the service offered being the exposure of these resources through EOSC (both the portal and potentially linked other marketplaces and catalogues). Here promises will be about how onboarding will be performed, how the resources will be exposed, the availability of the provider portal and also some crossover with the promises that can be made to users based on them.

The third agreement would cover providers offering core services to EOSC, the **Core Provider SLA**, needed to keep EOSC running, and cover the functions offered to the operators or owners of EOSC and EOSC portal. Functions might include EOSC AAI, monitoring and accounting, helpdesk and the provider and user

portals themselves. These functions will not be very apparent to EOSC customers and users, though will be exposed more to providers of research resources. These will have an impact on the Provider SLA and Exchange User Agreement, as both reply on EOSC core functions (such as the Marketplace and Provider portal platforms themselves, they web sites, monitoring and accounting etc

The fourth agreement is somewhat different to the others, as it covers the interaction with the resource registry held by EOSC with other (presumably smaller) community registries and portals. We could call this the **Resource registry Interaction OLA**. This is based on the systems of systems approach discussed above, and the need to shift data on resources from community registries to the central EOSC registry and vice versa. Here a different kind of agreement is needed, as rather than agreeing to provide data about and promises about their own resources, a community marketplace owner would instead need to assert that their resource listings were compliant with EOSC standards such that they did not need revalidation. This then would reply on the (assumed) SLA between the community marketplace owner and the provider of the resources they list (this last being outside the scope of this document, though could of course be modelled on the Provider SLA) which we might call the Community Provider SLA.

Finally, there are **SLAs for Research Services**, any SLAs offered by providers of research resources for their services or other resources, which EOSC is not involved in though may support. These are included for completeness of the picture but are not in scope for EOSC, as EOSC, through the EOSC Association or otherwise, does not at present intend to put itself between customers and providers of research resources, rather facilitating, mediating and supporting access to services. However, EOSC may support research resource providers in creating, maintaining and delivering on SLAs by offering templates, knowledge and training material.

While complex, this structure is needed to capture the web of services, resources and relationships needed to operate the imagined EOSC. It relates to the ongoing work of the Sustainability WG, describing a complex landscape that is broken down into a Minimum Viable EOSC, and anticipates that SLAs/OLAs, etc, will be required in order to deliver that complexity, taking an iterative approach.

4.2 Changing stakeholders in the period 2020-2028

In addition to the different agreement types and different roles, we see the stakeholders who take on these roles will change over the period from now until the end of Horizon Europe. This is due to how EOSC is being built, initially from a series of existing entities or projects, transiting over time to longer term central or community legal entities and associations. Over time, this should improve the situation as with less projects and more long-term sustainable entities, EOSC will be more reliable and stable. In addition, these entities will be better placed to make promises about how services are delivered, and to make formal agreements on this.

The following table summarises how we see the assignments of stakeholders to roles is likely to evolve. In dealing with this evolution, while we see the basic agreement structure will be stable, changes of stakeholders will require the re-signing if not renegotiation of the agreements.

Table 1: Changing stakeholders and roles in EOSC agreements

Entity	Stakeholder: 2020	Stakeholder: 2021-2023	Stakeholder: 2028
EOSC Portal Owner	Members of EOSC portal collaboration (EOSC Enhance, EOSC-hub, OpenAIRE Advance projects)	EOSC Association AISBL plus EOSC Enhance and INFRAEOSC-03 project	EOSC Association AISBL
Provider of Research services or other resources	Mixture of projects, organisations, associations.	Legal entities (organisations, associations etc)	Legal entities (organisations, associations etc)
Community marketplace owner (e.g. marketplaces from thematic cluster projects)	Projects (e.g. thematic cluster and national EOSC projects), some legal community organisations	Mix of projects and legal community organisations (e.g. ERICs).	Largely legal community organisations.
Provider of EOSC Core resources	Projects (EOSC-Hub, EOSC Enhance)	INFRAEOSC- 03 Project, some functions from other organisations under contract to EOSC Association.	EOSC Association AISBL internal resources or legal associations/organisations under contract to the EOSC Association AISBL

As a result of these foreseen evolutions of the stakeholders, the EOSC Association is likely to ‘inherit’ ownership of a number of agreements, and as such agreements should be planned to support this transfer.

Other key changes include a move from projects as stakeholders to associations or other legal entities. It seems likely that projects will continue to be important in building EOSC, mobilising actors and organising efforts, but projects have limitations in several areas which are starting to become problematic. This is seen in the drive towards entities such as ERICs, AISBLs, foundations and other legal structures to bind actors within the EOSC ecosystem, from the European Commission and other funders. It relates to a push toward sustainability and long term stability seen in the European Research Area. Projects cannot make long term agreements, and in fact cannot make formal binding agreements in most cases. They cannot assert ownership of IPR. For participants, project mandates simplified the management and organisation of many processes, as a proxy for longer term agreed structures and processes. However once the new bodies and groups have been created, a longer term solution is needed. Already organisations like the EUDAT Ltd. Stitching EGI and OpenAIRE AMKE are examples of legal entities born out of project series to provide longer term stability.

5 Exchange User Agreement and Provider SLA recommendations

The following table shows suggested / possible content for the Marketplace and Provider SLAs based on the model SLA content showed in an Appendix. It is not intended to represent agreed or final. Content in italics represents examples or possible content. We would foresee that in future the provider offering the SLA would be the EOOSC Association.

Table 2: Suggested content for the Marketplace and Provider SLAs

Section	General description of the section	Exchange User Agreement example content	Provider SLA example content
General	Sets out the parties to the agreement, both the individual and which entity they represent. Covers period of validity of the SLA, typically a year, to allow for annual review and possible update to the SLA.	This agreement is made between [<i>EOOSC portal user</i>], represented by [<i>Individual making account</i>] and [EOOSC Portal], represented by [<i>EOOSC Association AISBL</i>] to cover the provision and support of the service as described hereafter. This SLA is valid from [1/1/21]to [31/12/21].	This agreement is made between [<i>Resource provider</i>], represented by [<i>Legal entity</i>] and [EOOSC Portal], represented by [<i>EOOSC Association AISBL</i>] to cover the provision and support of the service as described hereafter. This SLA is valid from [1/1/21]to [31/12/21].
Scope and description of the service	Sets out what the service in question is. Will often link to a longer description of the service in a service catalogue.	This SLA applies to the following service: [<i>Access to the EOOSC Marketplace</i>] [<i>This comprises access to the EOOSC marketplace which lets customers and users access information about and compare EOOSC resources they may wish to make use of. For selected resources these can then be ordered and/or their status monitored via the portal</i>]	This SLA applies to the following service: [<i>Exposure of resources though the EOOSC portal and other related linked portals</i>] [<i>This comprises exposing the resources from a resource provider through EOOSC, both directly through EOOSC Marketplace and indirectly through other community marketplaces. Additional options including ordering of services by Marketplace users and integration with EOOSC core service are available as options</i>]
Service hours and exceptions	Sets out under what hours the service normally operates. Most IT services will operate 24/7 but e.g	The EOOSC Marketplace is normally available 24 hours a day, 7 days per week. However,	The EOOSC Provider portal is generally available 24 hours a day, 7 days per week. However,

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	<p>some banking services such as money transfer services operate only during office hours. Training and consultancy services also typically only operate during office hours.</p> <p>Sets out expected exceptions to service hours, both planned closures and time the service may operate but cannot be guaranteed. Typically mentions holidays, annual closures and regular maintenance windows.</p>	<p>availability is not guaranteed during the following periods:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - During seasonal holiday periods including <i>DAY to DAY (full list available at URL on EOSC Portal)</i> - During planned maintenance windows including <i>the first Monday of each month, and the first week of July and December</i> 	<p>availability is not guaranteed during the following periods:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - During seasonal holiday periods including <i>DAY to DAY (full list available at URL on EOSC Portal)</i> - During planned maintenance windows including <i>the first Monday of each month, and the first week of July and December</i>
Service component and dependencies	<p>Sets out what technical components make up the service which the customer may need to be aware of. In particular highlight any dependencies on other services.</p>	<p>The service covered by this SLA is made up of the following (technical and logical) service components:</p> <p><i>The EOSC Marketplace includes the EOSC Portal Website, EOSC Marketplace platform, EOSC Ordering system and the EOSC Portal AAI system used to authenticate against the portal.</i></p>	<p>The service covered by this SLA is made up of the following (technical and logical) service components:</p> <p><i>The EOSC Provider portal includes the EOSC Portal website, EOSC Provider Portal platform, EOSC registry APIs and the EOSC Portal AAU used to authenticate against the portal. . Additional Service Components are required for additional integration with EOSC Core services, and are optional, based on the desired degree of integration.</i></p>
Support	<p>Explains during what hours support is available for the service, as distance to when the service operates. Often support will be weekday office hours</p>	<p>The services covered by the scope of this SLA are provided with the following level of support:</p>	<p>The services covered by the scope of this SLA are provided with the following level of support:</p>

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	for regular services, and only 24/7 for high impact or critical services.	<p><i>Support for the EOSC Marketplace is available 9am – 5:30 pm CE(S)T from Monday to Friday.</i></p> <p><i>Support outside of these ours is on a best effort basis outside of special circumstances.</i></p> <p><i>Support is also on a best effort basis over between XX December and XX January each year, and on other holidays listed at URL.</i></p>	<p><i>Support for the EOSC Provider Portal is available 9am – 5:30 pm CE(S)T from Monday to Friday.</i></p> <p><i>Support outside of these ours is on a best effort basis outside of special circumstances.</i></p> <p><i>Support is also on a best effort basis over between XX December and XX January each year, and on other holidays listed at URL.</i></p>
Support: Incident Handling	Explain how different types of incident will be handled according to their priority (based on their impact). May refer to a separate document for more detailed prioritisation.	<p>Disruptions to the agreed service functionality or quality will be handled according to an appropriate priority based on the impact and urgency of the incident. In this context, the following priority guidelines apply:</p> <p>Incidents will be handled according to the incident prioritisation and categorisation approaches.</p> <p><i>Low priority incidents (impact users but do not prevent service from operation). Target response time: 4 working days according to calendar at URL.</i></p> <p><i>Medium priority incidents (Impact service operation but do not entirely prevent use). Target response time: 1 working days according to calendar at URL</i></p> <p><i>High priority incidents (Entirely prevent service use, or are security related incidents) / Target response time: 4 working hours according to calendar at URL.</i></p> <p>Note: while the EOSC Helpdesk may escalate incidents to owners and operators of researcher facing services, it does not guarantee response or resolution times to these tickets as they are not under the control of the EOSC operator community or EOSC Association AISBL.</p>	
Support: Fulfilment of Service Requests	List the different standard service requests likely to be submitted by users (request for access,	In addition to resolving incidents, the following standard service requests are defined and will be fulfilled through the defined support channels.	In addition to resolving incidents, the following standard service requests are defined and will

	<p>information or pre-approved changes) and how they will be handled.</p>	<p>Initial service requests include:</p> <p><i>Password reset and other access issues.</i> <i>Block account (prevent it making service or other resource orders)</i> <i>Request for information or training on service not covered by current material.</i></p> <p>Response and fulfilment times are provided as service level targets</p>	<p>be fulfilled through the defined support channels.</p> <p>Initial service requests include:</p> <p><i>Password reset and other access issues.</i> <i>Block account.</i> <i>Request for information or training on service not covered by current material.</i> <i>Connect community AAI to EOSC (portal) AAI.</i> <i>Begin integration with a core service (e.g. accounting, monitoring helpdesk, CMBD).</i></p> <p>Response and fulfilment times are provided as service level targets</p>
<p>Service Level Targets</p>	<p>This section sets out measurable targets offered for the services listed, which can be monitored and reported on.</p>	<p>The following are the agreed service level targets for [name of the service]:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Overall availability – 99%</i> - <i>Response to High priority incidents and Service Requests: 4 working hours</i> - <i>Response to medium priority Incidents and Service Requests: 1 working day</i> - <i>Response to low priority Incidents and Service Requests: 4 working days</i> - <i>Response to service orders: 2 working days</i> 	<p>The following are the agreed service level targets for [name of the service]:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Overall availability – 99%</i> - <i>Response to High priority incidents and Service Requests: 4 working hours</i> - <i>Response to medium priority Incidents and Service Requests: 1 working day</i> - <i>Response to low priority Incidents and Service Requests: 4 working days</i> - <i>Response to requests to validate a new resource provider organisation: 3 working days</i> - <i>Review of resource information updates following a suspension: 2 working days</i>

<p>Limitations and constraints</p>	<p>This section provides limitations on use of services or on customers and users not stated elsewhere, often workload limits or types of permitted use.</p>	<p>The provisioning of the service under the agreed service level targets is subject to the following limitations and constraints:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Customers and users must comply with the EOSC Rules of Participation, including following relevant Terms of Use for the Marketplace and for the resources they access through it.</i> • <i>Resources should be accessed for the purposes of supporting research, and only legal activities can be performed through EOSC.</i> 	<p>The provisioning of the service under the agreed service level targets is subject to the following limitations and constraints:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Resources connected to EOSC must comply with EOSC Rules of Participation and inclusion criteria for the EOSC Marketplace and registry.</i>
<p>Communication reporting & escalation: General communications</p>	<p>This sets out communications channels for communication in either direction between the provider and customer.</p>	<p>The following contacts will be generally used for communications related to the service in the scope of this SLA:</p> <p>Customer contact for the service provider: <i>Email address from customer registration</i> Service provider contact for the customer: <i>catalogue@eosc-portal.eu</i> : Service provider contact for service users: <i>catalogue@eosc-portal.eu</i> :</p>	<p>The following contacts will be generally used for communications related to the service in the scope of this SLA:</p> <p>Customer contact for the service provider: <i>Provider organisational contact from Provider Profiles</i> Service provider contact for the customer: <i>providers@eosc-portal.eu</i> : Service provider contact for service users: <i>providers@eosc-portal.eu</i></p>

<p>Communication reporting & escalation: Regular Reporting</p>	<p>This section lists regular reporting to customers, and relates to Service Reporting Management as discussed earlier in this document. .</p>	<p><i>EOSC Marketplace annual report</i> - Sent to all registered Marketplace users once per year by email – webpage and link to pdf. Covers overall growth and usage of resources linked through the Marketplace and the Marketplace itself during the year. Summarised user and customer feedback and future plans.</p> <p><i>Individual Marketplace usage report</i> - Automatically generated quarterly usage report emailed to users to show which resources they used during the period and suggests other resources based on their prior usage, including new resources. Solicits feedback from users and customers.</p>	<p><i>EOSC annual provider report</i> - Sent to all registered providers once per year by email – webpage and link to pdf. Covers overall usage of resources through the marketplace and growth of use of the Provider portal through the year. Summarises provider feedback and future plans.</p> <p><i>Individual provider usage report</i> -Automatically generated quarterly report on usage of resources from a provider during the period. Emailed to provider contacts. Solicits feedback from providers.</p>
<p>Communication reporting & escalation: SLA Violations</p>	<p>This section describes the communication actions to be taken in case of future or actual SLA violation.</p>	<p>The service provider commits to inform the customer, if this SLA is violated or violation is anticipated. The following rules are agreed for communication in the event of SLA violation:</p> <p><i>If an SLA has been violated or we become aware it is likely to be violated, we will inform you using the contact channel provided in the general communications section above, as soon as possible.</i></p> <p><i>For major SLA violations and interruption of service, affected users and customers will receive a report after the fact to explain why the violation occurred, what was done to remedy it, and how its reoccurrence will be avoided in future. Major SLA violations will also be reported on in annual reporting.</i></p>	
<p>Communication reporting & escalation: Escalation and complaints</p>	<p>This section provides customers with the paths they can use to make complaints about services.</p>	<p>For escalation and complaints, the defined service provider contact point shall be used, and the following rules apply:</p>	

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		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>In the first instance customers should use the contact from the general communication section above.</i> - <i>If they do not find the response from the regular contact satisfactory, the following additional contacts can be used:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o <i>For issues related to inclusion of resources in the Marketplace, contact can be made with the Rules of Participation group within the EOSC Association at EMAIL.</i> o <i>For issues related to resources accessed through EOSC but not the portal or its components themselves, contact can be made with the Provider Quality team at EMAIL.</i> o <i>For issues related to the Portal, including the Marketplace and provider Portal, contact can be made with the Portal Administration team at EMAIL.</i> - <i>If neither the standard contact nor specialised contacts above are able to resolve the situation complaints can be directed to the EOSC association at EMAIL.</i> 	
Information Security & Data Protection	This section provides references to Information Security and Data Protection policies.	<i>Use of the EOSC portal services including the Marketplace and Provider Portal is governed by the EOSC Information security and Data Protection policy available at URL.</i>	
Additional responsibilities of the service provider	This section can be used for any additional responsibilities on the service provider which need to be stated or highlighted to customers.	<i>EOSC is an initiative funded in part by the European Commission, and provides reporting to the European Commission based on available information provided. This does not include sensitive provider or customer information but may include anonymised average data from users and providers, and metrics based on stated service level targets monitored for researcher facing services in the Marketplace.</i>	
Customer responsibilities	This section lists any additional responsibilities on customers of the service.	<i>Customers must abide by the terms and conditions of the services they use, both those from EOSC portal and those associated without resources they connect to through EOSC.</i>	<i>Customers must abide by the terms and conditions of the services they use, both those from EOSC portal and those associated</i>

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			<p><i>without resources they connect to through EOSC.</i></p> <p><i>Customers providing services to EOSC must agree to keep their resource information up top date. At a minimum this requires that information is updated twice per year, or when an urgent and important gap is identified (such as missing security information).</i></p>
Review	This sets out how frequently the SLA will be reviewed, and is tied to the period of validity in an earlier section.	<i>This SLA will be reviewed annually and proposed changes communicated to customers.</i>	
Glossary of Terms	This section provides or points to definitions of key terms used within the SLA.	Refer to glossary / role model on EOSC Portal based on input from community and glossary task force.	

6 Other SLA recommendations

6.1 Core Service Provider SLA recommendations

While we recommend that the Core Service Provider SLAs are of the same format as those seen above, we do not provide sample content as while in one sense they will be quite similar, the services they cover (e.g. AAI, helpdesk, monitoring and accounting, the marketplace and the provider portal) will vary depending on the topic and technical service. However, it is important that they support the promises made to customers of the Marketplace and Provider portal. For instance, the availability of the Core services cannot be lower than that promised through the Marketplace and Provider portal, in fact typically they should be higher, to account for unavailability for the whole system caused by e.g. technical integration flaws.

In determining these SLAs, the Portal owner (presumably ultimately the EOSC Association AISBL) should require service level targets from Core Service Providers which align with the demands of the customers of the Provider Portal and Marketplace.

6.2 Resource registry Interaction OLA recommendations

As discussed above, in order to fulfil the view of EOSC as a 'system of systems', it is necessary to accommodate and support multiple community portals and resource registries, but interconnect them such that they are interoperable, and information on resources can flow between them.

Here the service is a bit different, it is provision of a set of resource metadata from the community portal to EOSC portal (and vice versa) along with the operation of the APIs to make it transmissible.

Some part of the OLA would resemble the Provider Portal SLA, as it would cover similar content, but it would need some additional elements related to API availability. However, the biggest addition would be related to agreeing to common formats for provider and resource data (following the provider and resource profiles v3.0) and equally importantly, the agreement to engage in a common method of validation of resource profiles.

In order for data to flow freely between registries and portals, it cannot need to be revalidated each time it moves from one to another, as this would require orders or magnitude too much effort for efficient operation of EOSC, instead, validation following the EOSC Rules of Participation must be a shared approach used similarly by all portal owners. While Rules of Participation will provide high level guidance on this, it is unlikely, based on current plans, that it will provide detailed procedures for validation of resources and providers. Instead such detailed steps must be created through a community effort of the EOSC association, organisations supporting EOSC portal and owners of other community portals.

The key part of the agreement on this topic will be a commitment to participate in the creation of these community validation procedures and a commitment to use the agreed procedures.

6.3 Encouraging SLAs between users and providers of research services

In the course of onboarding and connecting resources to EOSC, the providers of research services are asked to provide a considerable amount of information, including the majority of the information that would be found in an SLA. Hence, onboarding already helps to increase IT Service Management maturity among providers of resources to research by requiring them to address ITSM issues. In the long run, it would be advantageous for Europe and the renewed European Research Area for all services to include an SLA, and for all other resources to include an appropriate licence.

While advantageous, there is a broad caution about SLAs within the research community, as there is little cultural adoption of the concepts of IT Service management, outside of some groups who have pursued it more actively. In particular, there is a general fear that an SLA implies a legal contract with penalties (presumably financial) for SLA violation. In fact this is not the case, and SLAs can be of a 'softer' type, which sets out expectations for how services are delivered. Such SLAs have already been used by some actors in the EOSC ecosystem for close to a decade, but the cultural shift to more understanding and expertise in IT Service Management is a slow process.

One alternative, explored within the EOSC-hub project, is to request or require a 'Service Level Specification', which has the same content as an SLA but more clearly is not an agreement, but a statement of service levels that can be expected. This would fit well with the way that SLAs are already in use in the research sector, and serves much the same role in managing services.

At present an SLA for Research Services (between a provider and end user/customer) is not a requirement for connecting and onboarding resources to EOSC, but on a practical level, well over half the information is required through the Provider and Resource profiles prepared by Enhance. Ultimately, it would be a positive step to require providers to state their service levels and potential service level targets to customers. It could drive providers to be more customer and user focussed, and it would build confidence in EOSC among research communities, without implying a need for 'enterprise-level', expensive commercial-style service level targets. In the research domain there is often a tolerance for much more limited service levels for, e.g., cutting edge beta research services which leverage new algorithms or approaches and are not expected to have the same service levels as, say, an organisational email service.

Taking a Service Level Specification as a mandatory element for onboarding, with incremental increase in what information is requested as EOSC matures, would make planned service quality transparent to users and customers, and would encourage greater service quality without requiring penalties beyond community feedback. This would also support the EOSC Marketplace to monitor and report against any service levels targets stated by a provider to be able to show their effectiveness.

If this direction is adopted, it would be advisable to include training and support material and activities in the EOSC ecosystem to assist resource providers. This could include a template SLS based on the material presented here as well as guides in how to generate the specific contents of it, and what is needed to make good on the promised an SLS would make.

7 Portal SRM recommendations

Service Reporting Management (SRM) is an important component in a Service Management system, driven by Service Portfolio Management and Service Level Management, both of which are closely related to the work of EOSC Enhance and the EOSC Portal in general. SRM's general purpose is 'To specify all service reports and ensure they are produced according to specifications in a timely manner to support decision-making⁵⁷. In practice this means to ensure that appropriate reporting is carried out, primarily towards customers, and generally based on the contents of the SLA. And in particular reporting on the performance versus the service level targets defined/ The purpose of SRM is not to generate additional reports which may not be read.

From the point of view of EOSC, reporting serves a number of purposes:

- To demonstrate to customers that the EOSC Portal meets its obligations, specifically around its services and agreements.
- To show the usage of the EOSC Portal to customers in order to demonstrate the relevance and value of EOSC to them
- To have an opportunity to solicit feedback from customers and to suggest further use of EOSC Resources which they can make

The output should be a relatively small number of reports which provide value but can be prepared with reasonable effort. A good initial suggestion would be an annual report on EOSC to each customer type (Marketplace customers and provider Portal customers) augmented by customer specific quarterly usage reports which can be largely if not entirely automatically generated.

Examples of suggested SRM promises are made in the section above including proposed SLA content.

8 Portal Privacy policy status

In the current era, there is a clear focus in society and the research community on the need to consider privacy and data protection perhaps best seen in the implementation of GDPR. This has been an important issue for EOSC portal for some time, and already considerable work has gone into addressing it.

The current status includes the following two documents, also included as appendices.

- Summary of Portal privacy policy <https://www.eosc-portal.eu/privacy-policy-summary>
- Full Portal Privacy policy <https://www.eosc-portal.eu/privacy-policy>

⁵ From FitSM 2 Objectives and Activities, edition 2016 v2.2. CC-BY <https://www.fitsm.eu/download/304/>

The current work on privacy policies for EOSC and ESOC portal have come from the earlier work on the EOSC Portal from the partners who later formed EOSC Enhance but continues to be periodically updated, with the current version from April 2020. The present approach seems sufficient to cover EOSC needs but will need to be revised in light of upcoming changes, including the launch of the provider portal, the revised EOSC Exchange and subsequent changes to the Portal web content.

In addition, there is a need to ensure that, as far as possible, providers of EOSC resources treat the data that they collect from customers with due care and according to regulations. While EOSC, as represented by a project or the EOSC Association, will of course exercise due diligence in dealing with any data it gathers, it will also be acting as a matchmaker or broker, connecting researchers and research groups to services which they see or potentially access via the exchange. Once connected, EOSC may no longer be a party to any discussion or engagement between the customer and provider, but there is a potential reputational risk for the EOSC portal and EOSC association if the provider does not act correctly with private data. It must be made clear where the limit of EOSC or EOSC Association AISBL responsibility lies, and that EOSC has no liability. At the same time, EOSC must encourage, to the greatest extent possible, correct handling of personal data by providers listing their resources with EOSC. While it is expected that this will feature in the EOSC Rules of Participation, it must be reviewed periodically.

9 Next steps and conclusions

EOSC Enhance is an integrating activity, building on the past and current work by a wide range of organisations, communities and projects, and flowing into the newly formed EOSC Association AISBL. Sources of content or elements of the portal include the partners of Enhance, other projects like EOSC-hub and OpenAIRE Advance, and EOSC governance structures. The latter include the Working groups, in particular those on Rules of Participation, Architecture and Sustainability, as well as some of the newer Interest Groups. EOSC Enhance has broad responsibility for elements of the portal within this larger context, but not authority to force changes in the wider community. Hence, it must work through agreement and consensus.

In general, we suggest an agreement structure which recognises that EOSC will offer services both to researchers (offering listing, search, access and order of researcher facing services) and to resource providers (offering the opportunity to list their services and other resources, and integrate with core services). This is complemented by additional supporting agreements (An SLA for Core Service providers and an OLA for integration and interaction with other portals). These can largely all be based on the same core content, presented in this document, with additional information required in each case to fit that specific relationship.

The work presented here will have an impact on a wide range of groups, and as such it cannot be presented as a finalised and fixed model and set of agreements, especially as we foresee change in the stakeholders taking on the various roles identified over the coming years. In particular, the EOSC Association will likely take on responsibility for many of these agreements, especially as projects cannot make such agreements, not being legal entities. Enhance will seek to cooperate with the EOSC Association as it develops in 2020-2021, in order to ensure the agreement structure it puts in place can be taken on by them.

In order to accommodate this situation, the results of this document will be shared for consultation via the EOSC Secretariat Interest Groups as a way to share information on the approach and solicit feedback on it.

Following this, and aligned with the updates to the EOSC Exchange (formerly marketplace) component and relaunch of the provider portal later in 2020, we will begin to implement this content as outline agreements for Portal customers, either of the Marketplace or Provider Portal.

It is likely that the first use will be implementation of an agreement with resource providers using the Provider Portal. Up to now, providers and their resources have been onboarded in a variety of different ways, and without explicitly agreements. As the Portal and community have evolved, both the additional requirements on providers and the additional value generating offerings to the providers have grown. An example is the shift to the newer and more Provider and Resource profiles 3.0, alongside the new planned obligation for providers to periodically update the data they submit about their resources.

The structure here will be offered for consultation by the community as a first step, to communicate the larger structure of agreements needed and prepare the way for their implementation later. With the launch of the new provider portal we intend to launch both a Provider SLA and Exchange User Agreement aligned to one another. These will likely be service level SLAs, that is to say they will apply to that service but be the same for all customers of it, and agreement to them will be required for and connected to the signup or onboarding process for these two services.

The Core Provider SLA and Resource registry Interaction OLA are expected to be launched in 2020, alongside work from the INFRAEOSC03 project and in collaboration with the EOSC Associations.

EOSC Enhance will report in future deliverables (including annual and final reports) on the evolution of the work presented here based on community feedback, and the implementation of this agreement structure.

10 Appendix A: General structure of SLAs and OLAs

This section provides the general structure of an SLA or other agreement based on it.

10.1 Notes on SLA template

The template in the following sections is, on the FitSM SLA template, a creative commons template for SLAs suited to the EOSC community. While for some in the community, typical SLA contents may be familiar, it is worth providing a basic for those newer to the concepts or to act as a basic consensus structure for future discussion of SLA contents. This material is licensed under a CC-BY license⁶.

The content in the following section is based on providing a single service but can be adapted to multiple services. In addition, it can be used almost as-is as an OLA or UA template, as these will typically follow the same structure.

⁶ Available from <https://www.fitsm.eu/download/357/>

10.2 Example content of SLA on [service]

10.2.1 General

This agreement is made between [customer name], represented by [customer representative] and [service provider name], represented by [service provider representative] to cover the provision and support of the service as described hereafter.

This SLA is valid from [date] to [date].

10.2.2 Scope & description of the service

This SLA applies to the following service:

[Name of the service plus references to the service catalogue]

[Brief description of the service that is subject to the scope of this SLA, e.g. based on information in the service catalogue]

10.2.3 Service hours & exceptions

The service operates during the following hours:

[Service hours]

The following exceptions apply:

[Any exceptions from the regular service hours such as maintenance windows or other planned interruptions]

10.2.4 Service components & dependencies

The service covered by this SLA is made up of the following (technical and logical) service components:

[List and description of relevant service components at appropriate level of detail]

10.2.5 Support

The services covered by the scope of this SLA are provided with the following level of support:

[Details on support contact points and their hours of operation]

10.2.5.1 Incident handling

Disruptions to the agreed service functionality or quality will be handled according to an appropriate priority based on the impact and urgency of the incident. In this context, the following priority guidelines apply:

[Specific prioritization guidelines]

Response and resolution times are provided as service level targets (see section 5).

10.2.5.2 Fulfilment of service requests

In addition to resolving incidents, the following standard service requests are defined and will be fulfilled through the defined support channels:

[List of defined standard service requests]

Response and fulfilment times are provided as service level targets (see section 5).

10.2.6 Service level targets

The following are the agreed service level targets for [name of the service]:

Service level parameter	Target
Overall service availability	[Overall availability target]
[Parameter]	[Target]

10.2.7 Limitations & constraints

The provisioning of the service under the agreed service level targets is subject to the following limitations and constraints:

- [Workload limits]
- [Other limitations]

10.2.8 Communication, reporting & escalation

10.2.8.1 General communication

The following contacts will be generally used for communications related to the service in the scope of this SLA:

Customer contact for the service provider	[Contact details]
Service provider contact for the customer	[Contact details]
Service provider contact for service users	According to defined support channels

10.2.8.2 Regular reporting

As part of the fulfilment of this SLA and provisioning of the service, the following reports will be provided:

Report title	Contents	Frequency	Delivery
[Title]	[Brief specification of the contents]	[Frequency]	[Addressee and method of delivery]

10.2.8.3 SLA violations

The service provider commits to inform the customer, if this SLA is violated or violation is anticipated. The following rules are agreed for communication in the event of SLA violation:

[Rules for dealing with SLA violations]

- Escalation & complaints

For escalation and complaints, the defined service provider contact point shall be used, and the following rules apply:

[Rules for escalation and complaints]

10.2.9 Information security & data protection

The following rules for information security and data protection apply:

[Rules for information security and data protection - best practice applied ensuring that confidentiality, integrity and availability of the personal data is ensured]

10.2.10 Additional responsibilities of the service provider

[List and specification of any additional responsibilities or liabilities of the service provider]

10.2.11 Customer responsibilities

[List and specification of any specific customer responsibilities]

10.2.12 Review

There will be reviews of the service performance against service level targets and of this SLA at planned intervals with the customer according to the following rules:

[Rules (including frequency) for service reviews with the customer]

10.2.13 Glossary of terms

For the purpose of this SLA, the following terms and definitions apply:

[List of terms and definitions and / or reference to an external glossary]

10.2.14 Document control

Document ID	[Unique document identifier]
Document title	SLA on [service]
Definitive storage location	[Storage location, e.g. URL of the file on a server or document management system]
Document owner	[Name of the person primarily responsible for maintaining and reviewing this document]
Version	[Version]
Last date of change	[Date]
Next review due date	[Date]
Version & change tracking	[Version history & simple change log]

11 Appendix B: EOSC Portal Privacy Policy Summary

The following is taken from <https://www.eosc-portal.eu/privacy-policy-summary> as of 25/8/2020

Privacy Policy summary

EOSC Portal Privacy Policy
This website collects some Personal Data from its Users

Some of the data gathered from the platform is obtained via the use of third-party services. The data collected and how this is used is listed below:

User contact details
User contact form
Personal Data acquired: name, surname, email, country, and various typologies of data.

Statistics
Google Analytics, Hotjar Analytics
Personal Data gathered: Anonymous IP address. Cookies and usage data, heatmapping, navigation recording, and location.

Tag management
Google Tag Manager
Personal Data acquired: Cookies and data on usage

Contact management and communications
Newsletter
Personal Data gathered: email, name and surname
Managed by Trust-IT Srl

Feed Management
RSS
Personal data gathered: Cookies and data on usage

Interaction with social networks
Like button and Facebook social widgets, Tweet button and Twitter and AddThis social media widgets
Personal Data gathered: Cookies and usage data

Data acquisition and third-party platforms
Mailchimp Widget
Personal Data gathered: email, name, surname
Managed by Trust-IT Srl

[View the complete Privacy Note](#)

Effective Date: November, 5th 2019 - Ver 1.3

12 Appendix C: EOSC Portal full Privacy Policy

The following text is taken from <https://www.eosc-portal.eu/privacy-policy> as of 25/8/2020

Privacy Policy of EOSC Portal

The EOSC Portal platform, URL: www.eosc-portal.eu, (hereinafter referred to as "Site" or "Application") abides by the following principles when handling personal information:

We collect a small amount of personal information about our users in order to provide them with our content, products and services;

We limit the sharing or disclosure of this personal information to our needs or to comply with applicable legal requirements;

We give users meaningful choices over the use of their personal information;

We strive to protect the personal information that we hold.

This Privacy Notice describes the policies applied with respect to the personal information collected through the Site, or when the Site communicates with its users ("you" or "user"), and the choices that are made available to them. "Personal Information" means any information that relates to an identified or identifiable individual.

The project is co-funded by the European Commission, therefore the EU data processing law applies. The policy on "protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data by the Community institutions" is based on EU regulation as described https://ec.europa.eu/info/legal-notice_en#personal-data-protection

1. Your consent

Your use of the Site signifies that you agree will all terms of this Privacy Notice. If you communicate with us and provide us with personal information, we will assume that you agree that we can use this information to communicate with you. If you disagree with any part of this Privacy Notice, please do not use the Site or communicate with us.

2. Scope

This Privacy Notice applies solely to personal information that the Application collects through the Site or through any electronic communications that you send to the Application, as indicated on the Site (Personal Data). It does not apply to the websites of third parties, such as business partners or sponsors, to which the Site may link. The Application does not endorse, nor is responsible for the content of these third-party websites, or their policies or practices.

If you provide any personal information to or through third party websites, your transaction will be subject to the terms and conditions and the privacy policies of these third-party websites.

3. What information we collect, and how we collect it

The Application manages different types of data, all in compliance with the current European legislation on Data Protection. Any Data concerning the User is collected to enable the Owner to provide its services, as well as for the following purposes: Tag Management, Displaying content from external platforms, Analytics, Contacting the User, Managing contacts and sending messages, Interaction with data collection platforms and other third parties.

The Personal Data used for each purpose is outlined in the specific sections of this document.

Among the types of Personal Data that this Application collects, by itself or through third parties, are: Cookies, Usage Data, first name, last name, email address, various types of Data and Country.

Data voluntarily supplied by the User -- The web platform is designed to allow users to browse through it without providing any contact information. However, certain areas may require, or allow for, the submission of personal information, such as when a user fills out a newsletter form or contacts us. As an example, clients of the Application need to register to become part of the web site community and use the Application solutions.

The data collected and further processed are necessary to access the Application, as well as for communication and follow-up activities. Appropriate, detailed information is provided to the User and, where required, consent for the processing of Personal Data is obtained before a given service is activated. Said consent may be revoked at any time, whereby the ability to use the service in question ceases.

Users are responsible for any third-party Personal Data obtained, published or shared through this Application and confirm that they have the third party's consent to provide the Data to the Owner.

Cookies -- Any Cookies or other tracking tools used by this Application, or by the owners of third-party services used through this Application, serve the purpose of providing the service required by the User, in addition to any other purposes described in the present document and in the Cookie Policy, if available.

4. Interaction with social networks and external platforms

This kind of service allows you to interact with social networks, or other external platforms, directly from the pages of this application. The information acquired by the Application through this interaction is in any case subject to the User's privacy settings related to each social network. If an interaction service with social networks is installed, it is possible that, even if the Users do not use the service, the latter collect traffic data relating to the pages in which it is installed. Like button and Facebook social widgets (Facebook, Inc.)

The "Like" button and Facebook social widgets are services of interaction with the social network Facebook, provided by Facebook, Inc.

Personal Data collected: Cookies and Usage Data.

Place of processing: USA - Privacy Policy

Tweet button and Twitter social widgets (Twitter, Inc.)

The Tweet button and Twitter social widgets are services of interaction with the Twitter social network, provided by Twitter, Inc.

Data acquisition and third-party platforms: Mailchimp Widget

Place of processing: USA - Privacy Policy

Personal Data gathered: email, name, surname

Managed by Trust-IT Srl

5. Where and How the Data is processed

Location The Data is processed at the Data Controller's operating offices and in any other places where the parties involved in the processing are located. For further information, please contact us at privacy@eosc-portal.eu

Duration of Processing -- Data processing is limited to the time necessary to perform the service requested by the User. Unless otherwise requested by the European Commission, any data kept to the purposes of a project is retained for the duration of the project, plus the period requested by the European Commission (typically 3 years) after the project end. However, the User can ask at any time to interrupt the processing of the Data or have Data cancelled.

Log information-- Our server software automatically gathers general information from all users. For example: IP address, computer type, screen resolution, OS version, domain name, location, date and time of the visit, page(s) visited, time spent on a page, website from which the user came, action taken by the user when leaving our Site. Some of this information is provided directly by the user's browser, the remainder is obtained through cookies and tracking technologies.

Registration information -- Webinars and other events may be provided with the assistance of unaffiliated third-party vendors, which may require that the vendors have access to personal information such as name, company, and email address. These vendors will provide us with this information, so that we can keep track of who registers to, or attends these events. In this case, the information that you provide as part of this registration will be subject to both our Privacy Notice and the applicable privacy statement posted on the vendor's website.

Children -- The Site is not intended for children. Nor does the Application knowingly collect personal information from children.

6. How we use this information

The Application uses personal information for the following:

Fulfilment of requests -- We may use your personal information to deal with your inquiries, register you to our events, and send you the publications or documents that you request.

Internal business purposes -- We may use the collected information for internal business purposes, such as for audits or to track attendance at events.

Site operation -- We use cookies to assign a unique identifier to a user's computer.

Statistical analysis -- We use aggregated data about Site usage (which do not identify a specific user), such as the number of users who have visited certain pages of the Site, or how long users are spending on a particular page, in order to develop statistics as to the use of the Site, so that we can understand how users interact with the Site, to improve its content, products, or services.

Displaying content from external platforms

7. To whom your personal information is disclosed

The Data Controller processes the Data of Users in a proper manner and takes appropriate security measures to prevent unauthorized access, disclosure, modification, or destruction of the Data.

Data Controller: Alasdair Reid

European Future Innovation System Centre

Avenue Maurice Maeterlinck, 12

1348, Louvain-la-Neuve

Belgium

The Data processing is carried out using computers and/or IT enabled tools, following organisational procedures and practices strictly related to the purposes indicated. The Data Controller processes the Data of Users in a proper manner and shall take appropriate security measures to prevent unauthorized access, disclosure, modification, or unauthorized destruction of the Data. In addition to the Data Controller, in some cases, the Data may be accessible to certain types of persons in charge, involved with the operation of the site (administration, sales, marketing, legal, system administration) or external parties (such as third-party technical service providers, mail carriers, hosting providers, IT companies, communications agencies) appointed, if necessary, as Data Processors by the Owner. The updated list of these parties may be requested from the Data Controller at any time.

The Application Members -- We may share personal information with members of a Consortium for the purpose of creating a knowledge base and potential customer leads for the exploitation of results and assets.

EOSC Portal Marketplace Database (Managed by Cyfronet): the user unique identifier, first name, last name, email, reason for accessing EOSC services, country of origin, customer typology,

organization/company, country of collaboration, webpage, ordered services, messages (communication with support team), user rating information

In particular the list of users who indicated their interest in receiving the EOSC newsletter is shared with the newsletter responsables at the EOSC Enhance project and managed via the Data acquisition and third-party platform Mailchimp.

Law enforcement; compliance -- We may use or disclose personal information to any third party (a) if we believe that we are required to do so by law; (b) to comply with legal processes or respond to requests from governmental or public authorities; (c) to prevent, investigate, detect, or prosecute criminal offenses or attacks on the technical integrity of the Site or network; (d) to enforce our Terms and Conditions; or (e) to protect the rights, privacy, property, business, or safety of the Application, its business partners, employees, members, Site users, or the public. Unless prohibited by applicable law, we will inform you if a third party requests access to personal information about you.

8. Right to access and rectification

You have the right to have access to the personal information that we hold about you, and to have this information corrected and amended, as defined in the GDPR art. 12, 15, 16. To do so, please contact us as indicated in section 16. However, please be aware that in some cases, the administrative and technical burden associated with the retrieval of archived data may be substantial. We would need to be compensated for this effort in a manner that is consistent with our actual cost.

9. Right to erasure

You have the right to request that we delete any Personal Information that we hold about you. The Application is compliant with the Right to Erasure as defined in the GDPR, art. 17. If you would like us to erase the Personal Information that we hold about you, please contact us at privacy@eosc-portal.eu

10. Right to object

You have the right to object at any time to the processing of your personal data, on grounds relating to your particular situation, as defined in the GDPR, art. 21. Please note that all the data you provide on this website will be used only for delivery of the services provided by the Application, as described in section 5. If you would like to apply your right to object, please contact us by email at privacy@eosc-portal.eu .

11. Retention of information

We will retain personal information about a user for as long as necessary to fulfil the purposes outlined in this Privacy Notice, unless a longer retention period is required by law and/or regulations. The User can always request that the Data Controller suspend or remove the data.

12. Security

The Application seeks to adopt commercially reasonable security measures consistent with industry practice to protect personal information under its control against loss, misuse, and alteration. However, we cannot guarantee the security of our servers, the means by which personal information is transmitted between your computer and our servers, or any personal information that we receive through or in connection with the Site.

We attempt to strike a reasonable balance between security and convenience. Emails are usually sent as unencrypted text. If misrouted or intercepted, an unencrypted email could be read easily. If there is a matter that requires high security or confidentiality, please keep us informed about the sensitivity of the information, and do not send the related information by email.

13. Jurisdiction

The Application does not represent or warrant that the Site is appropriate or available for use in any particular jurisdiction. Those who choose to access the Site do so on their own initiative and at their own risk, and are responsible for complying with all local laws, rules, and regulations that apply to them.

We may limit access to the Site to any person, geographic area, or jurisdiction that we choose, at our sole discretion.

14. Inquiries and Complaints

If you have any questions, comments, or complaints about this Privacy Notice, or the use, management or disclosure of personal information collected on or through our Site, please contact us at privacy@eosc-portal.eu.

15. Updates to the Privacy Notice

We update this Privacy Notice from time to time. If the changes are significant, we will post prominent notification on this Site for a reasonable time to inform you of these changes. Unless, and until, you object in writing, by contacting us at privacy@eosc-portal.eu, all changes will apply to the existing information about you that the Application already holds, and the personal information collected from the effective date of the

revised Privacy Notice. Your use of the Site following the effective date of any revision will constitute your acceptance of the terms of the updated Privacy Notice.

16. How to contact Us

If you have any questions, comments, or complaints, regarding this Privacy Notice, or our privacy, security or data protection practices, please contact us by email at privacy@eosc-portal.eu

Effective Date: 30 April 2020 - Ver 1.4

List of acronyms / abbreviations used in this document

Acronym	Meaning
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ITSM	IT Service Management System
OLA	Operational Level Agreement
SLA	Service level Agreement
SLM	Service Level Management
SLT	Service Level Target
SMS	Service Management System
SRM	Service Reporting Management
UA	Underpinning Agreement